

DFC ACTIVITIES FOR IN-HABIT

Design for Change Spain takes part in the European project IN-HABIT (INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies) with a strong commitment to promote social inclusion, creativity and citizen empowerment through innovative educational methodologies. We promote from our experience processes that place children and youth as protagonists of change, recognizing their potential to actively contribute to the construction of more equitable, sustainable and cohesive communities.

This guide has gathered a set of dynamics and activities designed to facilitate spaces for participation, reflection and collaboration in both face-to-face and virtual contexts. These are versatile proposals, adaptable to different ages and formats, which can be used in group sessions, training days or community meetings; with the aim of strengthening teamwork, encouraging critical thinking and cultivating a culture of respect, active listening and creativity. Those who facilitate these spaces are invited to use this guide as a flexible tool, adjusting it to the characteristics and needs of each group. We are confident that these dynamics will contribute to enriching collective processes and consolidating healthier and more inclusive environments where all voices are taken into account.

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Face-to-face activities (Physical dynamics)

1. Presentation with superpowers

1.1 Objective

- Breaking the ice creatively.
- Introducing some key fundamentals of Design for Change: Divergence, convergence and synthesis; present in all phases of the DFC methodology.
- Encouraging collaboration and non-verbal expression.

1.2 Duration

- 25-30 minutes.

1.3 Materials

- Templates with questions (1 per participant).
- Pens.
- Space to move.

1.4 Development

- Phase 1: Divergence (individual responses)

Template delivery: Each participant receives a sheet with the questions:

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- How do you like to take naps?
- What phrase do you love to say?
- What superpower would you like to have?

Time to write (3 min):

The answers are anonymous.

Fold the sheet 3 times to hide the contents.

Collection and redistribution: All the pages are mixed and distributed at random (preventing someone from receiving theirs).

- Phase 2: Convergence (find the owner)

Participants should talk to each other to find out who wrote each sheet.

Key clue: "It's not about guessing, but about asking and connecting."

In the end, everyone must recover their own leaf.

- Phase 3: Synthesis (grouping by superpowers)

Form groups by similar superpowers (e.g. "fly" and "teleport" = mobility).

If someone is left alone, nothing happens (you can join a related group).

- Representation without words:

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Each group prepares a physical action to represent their superpower.

Everyone should participate in the representation.

- Group guessing:

The other teams try to figure out what superpower they represent.

- Reflection (linking with DFC):
 - Divergence: Individual responses (diversity of ideas).
 - Convergence: Find common patterns (grouping by superpowers).
 - Summary: Create a unique representation (collaborative solution).
- Key questions:
 - "How did you feel looking for the owner of the answers?" (Active listening).
 - "What was more difficult: Generating ideas or synthesizing them into an action?"

1.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- It facilitates active listening.
- It awakens curiosity in other people.
- It introduces the fundamentals of Design for Change.

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2. Low Tech Network

(Adaptation of Gamestorming for the Design for Change (DFC) methodology)

2.1 Objective

- Break the ice creatively and quickly.
- Encourage active listening and emotional connection.
- Introduce some of the capabilities that are developed with DFC: Boundless creativity and empathy.

2.2 Duration

- 15-20 minutes.

2.3 Materials

- Blank pages or cards (1 per person).
- Markers or pencils.
- Markers or pencils..

2.4 Development

- Phase 1: Creating the "Low Tech Profile" (3 minutes)

Each participant draws or writes in their folio:

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- A symbol or drawing representing you (e.g. a sun, a book, an animal). Remind participants that “all people are creative” regardless of the outcome.
 - Their name (large and visible).
 - 3 hashtags about topics they want to talk about (eg: #trips #football #recipes).
- Phase 2: Interaction in pairs (fast rounds)

First round (3-4 min per couple):

- Person A: Explain their drawing, say their name and read their 3 hashtags.
- Person B: Choose 1 hashtag and ask about it (e.g. "What is your favorite recipe from your grandmother?").

Then they exchange roles.

- Rotation:

After each round, participants change pairs (make two or three rounds, depending on the time available).

- Phase 3: Group reflection

Key questions:

- "Why do we use a drawing instead of a phrase?": DFC Key: "Because it connects from the visual and emotional, not from the rational.
 - "Why do you choose the topics of conversation?": DFC key: "We listen before we act."
- Key tips for the Facilitator:
 - Fast pace! Use a timer for rounds (e.g. "Change in 3, 2, 1...!").

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- Do an example first: Draw something simple (e.g. a cup of coffee) and use curious hashtags (#endlesstabletalk).
- Online: Use short Zoom/Teams rooms and ask them to share their "profile" on the camera.

2.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- It breaks barriers: The drawing gives us the opportunity to communicate in another way.
- Real Listening: Hashtags help avoid uncomfortable questions.
- DFC Fundamentals: "First we understand (listen), then we draw (creativity), and finally we share (network)."

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3. "What I see, what I Feel" — Image-based reflection

3.1 Objective

Encourage personal expression, active listening and emotional connection through free interpretation of images. It's perfect for opening topics, concluding processes or reflecting on a lived experience.

3.2 Duration

- 20-40 minutes.

3.3 Materials

- A diverse set of printed images (can be repeated).
- Tip: Use cards from the game [Dixit](#) or other evocative images. Attention: Always check whether the images are free to use or have authorization. The ones offered [in this link](#) are only an example, it is not guaranteed that they are free to use.

3.4 Development

- Place the images on a large table or on the floor. Leave room for everyone to see.
- Propose a clear slogan related to the moment they are living. Examples:
 - "Choose an image that represents how you have felt doing this project."

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- “Look for an image that speaks of how you see the world today.”
 - “Choose the image that connects with the idea of change for you.”
- Ask each participant to choose an image. Remember: Repeated images can be chosen, and that's fine,—it usually generates different reflections!
 - One by one, people share the reason for their choice, briefly and sincerely. Invite them to listen actively, without interruptions or judgments.
 - Remember that there are no right or wrong answers: The important thing is the personal connection that each person establishes with the image.

3.5 Closing and reflection

You can finish with a quick round of keywords (“I’m going with...”), a phrase that picks up what has been experienced, or even a shared mental image: “If this group were an image now, what would it be?”

3.6 Variant or extra level

For online groups: You can use a collaborative whiteboard like Miro, Jamboard or Canva, and share a digital gallery of images there for them to choose from.

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4. My Party

4.1 Objective

- Teach how to give constructive feedback through formulas that avoid negative judgment and encourage collaborative improvement.
- Contrast the emotional impact of using "Yes, but..." vs. "Yes, and also...".

4.2 Duration

- 20-25 minutes.

4.3 Materials

- Whiteboard or flipchart to write down examples (optional).
- Symbolic ingredients for the "party" (balloons, sweets, etc.) (optional).

4.4 Development

Phase 1: "Yes, But..." (Destructive Feedback)

The facilitator announces: "I'm going to set up a party. The main ingredient is... balloons! You're all invited, but everyone has to say 'but' to my idea."

Examples of answers:

- "Yes, but the balloons make a horrible noise when they pop."

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- "Yes, but I'm allergic to them."
- Participants' turn:

2-3 volunteers propose their own ingredient (e.g., "chocolate"), and the group responds with "Yes, but...".

- Final question: "How did it feel to only receive 'buts'?"

Phase 2: The "Yes, and also..." (Positive Feedback)

Reformulation: "Now, we'll use 'Yes, and also...' to turn problems into solutions."

Examples with balloons:

- "Yes, and we can also use biodegradable balloons."
- "Yes, and we can also fill them with helium so that they do not bother us."
- Practice: The same volunteers repeat their ingredients, and the group responds with constructive ideas.
- Question: "What difference do you notice now?"

Phase 3: Pro Formula (Sue Walden Style)

Advanced Structure: "What I like the most about your idea is... [rating], and we could also... [improvement]."

Example:

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"What I like the most is how colorful they are, and we could also put on background music."

- Golden Rule:

You can only answer "THANK YOU" (feedback is a gift, it is not justified or discussed).

- Final reflection:

Key questions:

- "How many times in our everyday life do we use 'Yes, but...' without realizing it?"
- "How could you apply this to your projects or meetings?"

Important message: "Feedback is not an attack, it is a tool. If we start by highlighting the good and adding improvements, everyone gets better."

- Variants:

For online teams: Use Miro or Jamboard to write "buts" and transform them into "alsos".

For teamwork: Apply it to real ideas (e.g., "Yes, but this design is expensive" → "Yes, and we can also look for cheaper materials").

4.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- Breaks toxic dynamics: Replace criticism with construction.
- Easy to remember: Clear formulas to use at work or in the personal environment.
- Fun: The analogy of the party makes learning enjoyable.

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5. The Clap

5.1 Objective

Promote spontaneous coordination and team cohesion through a non-verbal challenge.

5.2 Duration

- 10-15 minutes.

5.3 Materials

- None (only the group's hands).

5.4 Development

- Initial instructions:

"Let's try to give a single clap in unison, all at once. Pay attention to the rules:"

- It is forbidden to speak, make signs or sounds to coordinate.
 - It is forbidden to set a previous pace (e.g.: Repeated claps until synchronized).
 - It is only allowed to observe, guess and connect with the group.
- Practice:

Let the team try freely (usually, the first clap is uncoordinated).

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Analyze: Does anyone assume non-verbal leadership? Do you look at each other?

Keys to achieve this (if they reach a mental block):

- "Look at each other's body language: How they are breathing, the tension of their body, the movement of their arms..."
- "Do not think too much; trust your group intuition."

When they manage to do it (or are close to it), ask, "What changed to make it work?"

- Reflection (optional):

"What was more difficult for you: To coordinate or to not be able to communicate as always?"

"How do we transfer this full attention to the workplace?"

- Variants to raise difficulty:

"Blind": Do it with your eyes closed (increases dependence on other senses).

"Double clap": Try to give two consecutive synchronized claps.

5.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- Powerful metaphor: The clap symbolizes unity.
- No hierarchies: No one leads, all participants are equally important.

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6. The raft

6.1 Objective

- Foster group connection, peripheral attention and mutual trust through nonverbal synchronization.

6.2 Duration

- 15-20 minutes.

6.3 Materials

- Adhesive tape or strings to delimit the space (optional).
- Wide space (e.g.: Room without obstacles).

6.4 Development

Phase 1: Initial Balance

- Preparation:

Demarcate a space on the floor where all participants can fit in without problem (e.g.: 2x2 meters—or 6x6 feet—for 10 people) (optional if the room already has a designated space).

- Explain the rules:

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- The raft must be balanced: Evenly distributed (without accumulating on one side).
- It is forbidden to speak, stand still or move in circles.
- Constant movement: Walking slowly, changing direction.

- First minutes:

Observe if the group is naturally distributed or if there are any “dead zones.”

Useful indications: "Notice how your movement affects the balance of the raft."

Phase 2: Total Synchronization

- New rule:

"If a person stops, everyone must stop in the shortest possible time, and the challenge is not to notice who was the first."

If someone moves when another is standing still, emphasize: "The raft is sinking! All as one."

Phase 3: Group Reflection

- Key questions:
 - "What strategies have you used to synchronize without speaking?" (e.g.: look at peripheral movement, feel space).
 - "How has your connection changed from beginning to end?"
 - "In which real life team situations do you apply this 'collective attention'?"
- Key concepts to highlight:

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- Trust: You don't need to see everything. The group guides you.
 - Common goal: The "raft" (group) remains balanced if everyone contributes.
 - Nonverbal communication: Sometimes, invisible signals are more powerful than words.
- Variants to Raise Difficulty:
 - "Blind raft": Some (or all) participants close their eyes, increasing mutual dependence.
 - "Miniature raft": Reduce space progressively to demand greater coordination.

6.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- Visual metaphor: The raft is the team; if someone "sinks", it affects everyone.
- Ideal for: Teams with lack of listening skills, new groups or to strengthen cohesion after conflicts.
- Adaptable: Works in both open spaces and virtual meetings (using gestures in camera).

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7. Selfie Challenge

7.1 Objective

- Explore the environment in a creative and fun way while encouraging teamwork and improvisation.

7.2 Duration

- 30-45 minutes.

7.3 Materials

- Phone with camera (one per team or per group).
- List of personalized scenes (adapted to the place).

7.4 Development

- Preparation:

Form teams of 4-6 people (or a single group if there are few people).

Deliver the list of scenes to act out. Adaptable examples:

If it is in a city (e.g. Madrid):

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- "Selfie with the statue of the Bear and the Strawberry Tree" (replacing the "wild animal").
- "Selfie in a spaceship" (using the futuristic design of a building).
- "Selfie with Clara Campoamor" (looking for her monument or plaque).

If it is in a natural environment (e.g. beach):

- "Selfie being attacked by seagulls."
- "Selfie in the middle of a tsunami" (with movement effects).
- Key rules:
 - Everyone should be in every photo.
 - Use the environment to simulate the scenes (e.g. lying on the ground to "float in space").
 - Digital photomontages are not allowed (only what is captured in the moment).
- Implementation:

Give 20-25 minutes to take the selfies.

The facilitator can act as judge or let the teams vote for the most creative photo.

- Reflection (optional):
 - "How have you organized yourselves to devise and capture the scenes?"
 - "What surprised you from your environment that you had not noticed before?"

7.5 Why does this dynamic work?

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- It breaks the routine: Ideal after hours of training or meetings.
- Creativity under pressure: Manage time and ideas as a team.
- Shared memory: The photos become funny memories.

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8. Emotional incoherence

8.1 Objective

- Reduce tension, encourage laughter and release stress by disconnecting words and emotions.

8.2 Duration

- 15-20 minutes.

8.3 Materials

- None.

8.4 Development

- Initial explanation:

"We're going to play at being incoherent: Saying one thing but conveying the opposite. For example, say 'I'm very happy!' with a funeral face, or 'I'm really angry' with a soothing voice."

Key rule: The more exaggerated the contradiction, the better!

- Way of playing:

Option A – Free:

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In turn, each participant chooses a phrase + an opposite emotion to express it.

Examples of phrases:

- "I love working on Monday mornings" (with a weary voice).
- "I feel really good after eating broccoli" (with disgust).
- "This is a disaster" (laughing out loud).

Option B – With cards:

Cards with emotions (joy, sadness, anger, surprise) and neutral phrases are distributed.

Everyone should read the phrase with the opposite emotion to the one they got.

- Group variant:

Absurd dialog: Two volunteers have a conversation where both are incoherent.

Example:

- A: "Me han ascendido, es lo peor que me ha pasado" (llorando de risa).
- B: "I'm so sorry, that's horrible news" (jumping for joy).
- Reflection (optional):
 - "How have you felt while forcing this incoherence? What was more difficult: the tone of voice or the gestures?"
 - "In which real situations does something similar happen to us (e.g. saying 'everything is going well' when it is not)?"

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- Key tips for the facilitator:
 - Fast pace: Prevent participants from thinking too much.
 - Exemplify: The facilitator must start with a couple of exaggerated phrases to break the ice.

8.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- Emotional Release: Laughter reduces cortisol (stress hormone).
- Body Awareness: Learning to identify how we express emotions.
- Ideal for: Stressed teams, after conflicts or at the end of intense days.

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9. Gesture, Gesture.gif

9.1 Objective

- Close a session creatively and memorably, allowing participants to express what they have learned or lived through body movement rather than just words.

9.2 Duration

- 10-15 minutes.

9.3 Materials

- Enough space to move.
- Optional: Background music (without lyrics) to create atmosphere.

9.4 Development

Version 1: "Unique gesture"

- Instructions:

"Think of a word that summarizes what you take with you from this session. Now, turn it into a body gesture or posture (without speaking)."

Examples:

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- "Learning" → Gestures as if opening an imaginary book.
- "Team" → Arms intertwined with colleagues.
- "Fun" → Jump with arms up.

- Implementation:

In turn, each participant makes his gesture once, while the rest watches.

Optional: Others can guess the associated word.

Version 2: "Gif Mode" (On loop)

- Animated variant:

"Now, repeat your gesture on a loop, as if you were an animated gif."

The facilitator can shout "Freeze!" to pause the scene and highlight some gestures.

- Quick reflection:

"What surprised you about the others' gestures?"

Version 3: "Living Sculpture" (The Favorite)

- Instructions:

A first volunteer makes their gesture and stays "frozen" in position.

The following participants join one by one, adding their gestures and adapting to the space to create a "moving group sculpture".

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When everyone is in position, each person speaks their word out loud (without moving).

- Visual effect:

The final sculpture will be a mosaic of emotions and learnings that comes alive with small repetitive movements (gif).

Key phrase: "This sculpture is the reflection of what we have built together today."

- Reflection (optional):
 - "Was it easier to express yourself with gestures or with words? Why?"
 - "What do you take with you when you see the final sculpture?"
- Variants:
 - "Collective Gesture": The group chooses a single word and creates a gesture together.
 - "Photo.gif": Record the sculpture in motion to send it as a reminder.
 - "Sound included": Add a sound or onomatopoeia to each gesture (e.g. "Clap!" for a high-five).

9.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- Inclusive: Ideal for shy or multicultural groups (body language transcends language barriers).
- Memorable: The image lasts longer than words.
- Energizing: Perfect to close with joy after intense days.

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10. Which one is my team?

10.1 Objective

- Divide groups in a playful and original way, encouraging interaction and good atmosphere from the first moment.

10.2 Duration

- 5-10 minutes.

10.3 Materials

- None.

10.4 Development

Choose one of the dynamics depending on the characteristics of the group.

"Eyes Parade"

- How to do it:

The participants are arranged in a line according to the color of their eyes, from the lightest to the darkest.

The facilitator "verifies" the order and comments curiosities:

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"Has anyone been surprised by someone else's eye color?"

To form the teams: The line is divided into groups of 3-5 people (e.g. the first 4, the next 4...).

Bonus:

If there are very similar colors, let them debate among them the order in which they are placed!

"Birthday Line"

- How to do it:

Participants are ordered by date of birth (day and month) without speaking. They must use gestures or signs.

Once aligned, each one says their date out loud. The facilitator takes advantage to:

Celebrate if someone's birthday is coming soon ("This team comes with a gift included!").

Point out coincidences ("You are astrological twins!").

To form teams: Group by seasons (spring, summer...) or by quarters.

- Variant:

Calculate who is the "youngest" person in the group (not counting the year).

"Curls Contest"

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- How to do it:

Form a line according to how straight or curly their hair is, from the straightest to the curliest (or frizzy).

If someone has no hair:

"You decide where to place yourself. Do you feel more like part of the straight or curly team today?" (It usually gets a few chuckles!)

To form teams: Divide the line into halves or thirds.

- Other fun ideas:

a) "Map of the Room"

Group according to place of birth (north/south/middle of the country or by countries). Ideal for multicultural teams.

b) "Shoe Parade"

Line up from the most formal to the most informal footwear. It's perfect for breaking the ice at professional events!

c) "Storm of tastes"

Ask: "Sweet or salty?" or "Beach or mountain?" and form teams according to preferences.

- Key tips for the Facilitator:

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- Make it agile: Do not spend more than 10 minutes on it.
- Take the opportunity to connect: Use comments like "Wow, the 'Rebel Curls' team has a lot of energy!"
- Include everyone: If someone clearly doesn't fit, let them choose their team! (e.g. "You're the wild card").

10.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- It breaks the ice naturally
- It encourages observation and curiosity
- It eliminates hierarchies and promotes inclusion
- It promotes non-verbal communication
- It creates shared stories
- It is flexible and adaptable

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11. Orchestra Conductor

11.1 Objective

- Enhance observation, group synchronization and teamwork through a discrete imitation game.

11.2 Duration

- 15-20 minutes.

11.3 Materials

- Ample space to form a circle (chairs are optional).
- Wanting to laugh and get carried away!

11.4 Development

- Preparation:

The group sits or stands in a circle. A person walks away (should not see or listen to the group).

The others secretly choose an "orchestra conductor", who will initiate movements (e.g. clapping, touching their nose, moving their shoulders).

Key rule: Everyone should copy the director naturally, without staring at him so as not to give him away.

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- The Detective Challenge:

The person who was outside enters and is placed in the center of the circle. He has 3 attempts to guess who the director is.

Meanwhile, the group continues to imitate the leader's movements (who must change them every 10-15 seconds).

- Resolution:
 - If they are right: The discovered director goes to the center.
 - If they fail: The group selects a new director in secret, and the detective comes out again.
- Key tips for the Facilitator:

Setting: "Imagine that we are an invisible orchestra. The director guides, but no one can know who he is."

- To make it difficult: The director can use subtle movements (winks, lift a finger).
- To facilitate: Allow the detective to ask questions like "Are they a man/woman?" (if the group is large).
- Reflection (optional):
 - "What strategies have you used to not give away the director?" (E.g. looking out the corner of the eye, following the peripheral rhythm).
 - "How did the detective feel? And the director?"
 - Applied metaphor: "At work, we sometimes follow 'rhythms' without knowing who marks them. How does it affect us?"

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- Variants:
 - "Broken mirror mode": The director makes different movements than the group (e.g. they touch their ear, the others their chin).
 - "Chaotic version": Two secret directors (the detective will have a difficult time!).
 - For children: Use sounds (snaps, whispers) instead of movements.

11.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- Peripheral attention: Trains the ability to detect non evident patterns.
- Teamwork: Requires complicity and non-verbal communication.
- Fun assured: Mistakes are funny and relax the atmosphere.

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12. From 10 to 1 – The Challenge of Active Listening

12.1 Objective

- Develop active listening, group patience, and nonverbal communication through a seemingly simple but deeply revealing challenge.

12.2 Duration

- 15-25 minutes.

12.3 Materials

- None (only the group and its coordination ability).

12.4 Development

- Initial explanation:

"We're going to count from 10 to 1 collectively. It seems easy, but there are two essential rules:

✓ Only one person can say each number (no overlapping).

✗ If two people say one number at a time, we start again from 10.

Let's go!"

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The group begins without further indications. Observe without intervening: How do they organize themselves? Do they talk to assign turns? Do they use visual signals?

- Key tips for the Facilitator:
 - If a "quick solution" arises (e.g. assign fixed turns), interrupt and ask: "Are you listening or just repeating a pre-established order? The challenge is not to reach 1, but to achieve it from mutual listening."
 - If there is frustration: "What is stopping you from moving forward? How could you feel it's time to speak without depending on words?"
- Subtle clues (if blocked):

"Try breathing together before each number" or "Observe the body language of others."

- Final Reflection: (Indispensable):
 - "Which strategies worked and which didn't?"
 - "How was the process of staying silent to listen instead of speaking in order to impose?"
 - "In which real situations do we act like today?"
- Key learnings:

"Active listening is not waiting for your turn, but creating spaces where the right voice comes up at the right moment."

- Variants to Deepen:
 - "Silent mode": Prohibited any prior verbal communication (only gazes and gestures).
 - "With closed eyes": Increases dependence on breathing and the group's sounds.

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- "Chaotic version": Count from 1 to 10 (being ascending, there is more tendency to overlap).

12.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- It breaks automatic patterns: The simplicity of the exercise highlights our shortcomings when listening.
- Powerful Metaphor: It is a microcosm about how teams work (voices that were overlapping, spontaneous leaders, people who are inhibited).
- Ideal for: Teams with communication problems, new groups or to close active listening workshops.

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13. Crossing the River

13.1 Objective

- Foster team cohesion, creativity and collaborative problem solving through a physical and strategic challenge.

13.2 Duration

- 20-30 minutes.

13.3 Materials

- Newspaper sheets or blank pages (1 per participant, except the last of each team, which will have 2).
- Tape or cones to mark the boundaries of the "river" (optional).

13.4 Development

- Preparation:

Delimit the "river": Mark two lines on the ground (with tape or imaginary) representing the two sides of the river. The distance should be sufficient to make the challenge possible but not easy (e.g. 5-10 meters).

Form teams of 4-6 people each.

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Distribute the materials: Each participant receives 1 newspaper sheet or page, except the last one in each row, who receives 2 sheets.

- Instructions:

"This is a river full of piranhas. If you step on the water, you sink. You can only use magic sheets (newspapers/pages) to cross. These leaves float, but if you step on them too long, they sink (they can't crawl). The whole team must get to the other side."

Rules:

- ✓ You cannot step on the ground outside the leaves.
- ✓ Sheets cannot be thrown randomly (they must always be in contact with at least one foot of a participant).
- ✗ It is forbidden to break or bend the leaves (unless the facilitator allows creativity).

- The challenge starts!

Teams must organized to:

- Move forward in a coordinated way, passing the leaves forward.
- Manage the limited resource (the last one has an extra sheet to facilitate the relay).

The facilitator notes:

- Does a spontaneous leader arise?
 - How do they physically support themselves (balance, grips)?
 - What strategies do they use (e.g. "human bridge", quick relays)?
- Completion:

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When a team manages to cross, they celebrates their success.

If a team "sinks" a leaf (stepping on the ground), they can restart from the last safe point or continue with a penalty (e.g. losing a leaf).

- Reflection:
 - "Which strategy worked the best? And what was the biggest mistake?"
 - "How did it feel to be physically dependent on your peers?"
 - "What role did each person assume (leader, coordinator, executor)?"
- Applied learning:
 - "In real projects, resources are limited (like the leaves). How do you redistribute them to move forward?"
 - "Trust in the team is literally the ground you step on."
- Variants to raise the difficulty:
 - "Rising River": Shorten the available time (e.g. "The river rises in 5 minutes").
 - "Blind": A team member goes blindfolded (they must guide them verbally).
 - "Fragile leaves": Use silk paper instead of newspaper (beware your feet!).

13.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- Tangible metaphor: The river represents real obstacles; the leaves, scarce resources.
- Encourages physical contact: Improves interpersonal confidence (e.g. holding on to balance).

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- Ideal for: New teams, groups with lack of synergy or to close team building sessions.

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14. Activities “Not by Chance, by Design”

14.1 Objective

- Generate the optimal conditions for each phase of the Design for Change (DFC) methodology: Feel, Imagine, Do, Evaluate and Share, using practical activities that encourage observation, creativity, collaboration and reflection.

14.2 Duration

- 5-15 minutes (depending on the activity).

14.3 Materials

- It is specified in each activity.

14.4 Development

FEEL PHASE (Empathize and define the problem)

- Activity: "Fact or solution?".
- Objective: Differentiate between real problems (facts) and solutions.
- Development:

Watch an example (e.g. [Project DFC “Trash bins at our height”](#)).

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Analyze groups of phrases by asking the question “Fact or Solution?”:

- "The bins are too high" → Fact (observation).
 - "The bins need to be lower" → Solution (proposal).
 - "It bothers me not being able to reach it" → Fact (feeling).
 - "I need help to reach it" → Solution (idea).
- Reflection: "Why is it important to identify facts before proposing solutions?"

IMAGINE PHASE (Activation: Awakening Creativity)

- Activity: “Evolutionary Rock, Paper, Scissors”.
 - Objective: Energize and break hierarchies.
 - How to play:
 - In pairs, best of 3.
 - The winner advances; the loser becomes their "cheerleader".
 - Final: Last round to the best of 5 with everyone cheering!
- Activity: “The Highest Tower”.
 - Materials: 10 post-its per team.
 - Instructions: In 3-5 minutes, build the tallest and most stable tower without using anything else.
 - Learning: Working under pressure and fast prototyping.
- Activity: “Flying Ship”.
 - Materials: 10 straws + masking tape.

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- Instructions: In 5 minutes, create an object that flies as far as possible.
- Key: Innovation with limited resources.
- Activity: "Passing the Energy".
 - Dynamic: In a circle, pass a "ball of energy" with gestures and "Kia!".
 - Variant: Use palms and eye contact to increase concentration.
- Activity: "Different uses".
 - Objective: Encourage creativity (Divergent ideation)
 - Development: Give alternative uses to an object, for example helmets (e.g. pot, hanger).
 - Key DFC: "The only wrong idea is the one that is not said, because the opportunity for someone else to build on it is lost."

Do (Take action)

- Activity: "1, 2, 3... Action!"
- Objective: Physically activate the group in less than 5 minutes and generate positive energy to take action.
- Instructions: "In 10 seconds, everyone should..."
 - Touch 3 different walls (or objects if the space is small).
 - High five with different partners.
 - Make a random animal sound (without repeating!).
- End: At the end, shout at the same time: "1, 2, 3... ACTION!" with a leap or victory gesture.

EVOLUATE (Reflect and evolve)

- Activity: "Relaxation".

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- Development: Breathing exercises (2-3 minutes) to calm the mind before reflection, to pay more attention to learning.

SHARE (Tell the lived experience)

- Activity: “Shifted Story”.
 - Objective: Active listening and collaborative synthesis.
 - Development: In a circle, each person adds a phrase to the story of what they have lived.
 - Instruction: Do not repeat, but do link with the previous phrase.
- Activity: “Story with Random Words”.
 - Materials: Word cards (e.g. "airplane", "rain", "hug").
 - Challenge: Create a slogan or title for a DFC project.

14.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- These dynamics work because they create the necessary conditions to work in each phase of the Design for Change (DFC) methodology, generating the optimal type of energy in the participants in each phase.

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15. Closing Dynamic: "Exit corridor"

15.1 Objective

- Close the day with positive energy and humor.
- Visualize the attitude with which each participant wants to start the next day.

15.2 Duration

- 10-15 minutes.

15.3 Materials

- Enough space to form two rows in front of each other (a "hallway").

15.4 Development

- Preparation:

Ask the group to form two parallel rows, leaving a corridor 1.5m (5 ft) wide between them.

Explain: "This hallway represents the transition between today and tomorrow. By going through it, each person will adopt the attitude they want to bring tomorrow—from the most serious to the most ridiculous. Creativity for the win!"

- Walk individually or in couples:

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Each person (or couple) walks through the hallway by turns expressing their attitude with gestures, movements or phrases (e.g.: Dancing, as a superhero, yawning, with robot steps, etc.).

Those in the ranks applaud, or cheer.

When they get to the end, each participant joins the line (rotating so that everyone has their turn).

- Group closure:

Final sentence: "Tomorrow, when you walk in the door, remember this moment and choose how you want to start."

- Reflection (optional):

"How did you feel expressing your attitude in front of the group? Do you think it can influence your attitude tomorrow?"

It highlights the importance of consciously choosing our energy when facing new challenges.

15.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- Breaks formality: Humor relaxes and strengthens connections.
- Visualizes the future: Physically and symbolically, participants "enter" into a new attitude.
- Inclusive: Allows those who prefer not to speak to participate.

Note: If space is limited, adapt the corridor to a circle where everyone passes through the center.

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16. Closing Dynamic: "The Connection Network"

16.1 Objective

- Generate an emotional and visual closure that reinforces the feeling of involvement within the group.
- Allow each person to express what they take with themselves from the session, highlighting the connections created.

16.2 Duration

- 15-20 minutes.

16.3 Materials

- Colored pieces of paper (1 per person).
- Thick markers..
- A ball of wool or resistant thread.
- Painter's tape (optional, to tape the papers).
- Mobile or camera for final photo (optional).

16.4 Development

- Individual preparation (5 min):

Each participant writes on their paper a word, phrase or emotion that summarizes what they have internalized from the session. Encourage them to use large, clear letters.

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- Form the network (10 min):

Ask the group to form a circle with the participants quite close to each other.

The facilitator holds the end of the wool and explains: "We're going to weave a net that symbolizes what unites us today. When they receive the wool, everyone will say their word out loud and then will pass it to another person, creating connections."

- Dynamic:

The facilitator throws the ball at a person in the circle, holding its end.

Whoever receives the wool says their word, holds it with one hand (leaving a tense section) and passes it to another companion (avoiding the immediate neighbors to create more crosses).

Repeat it until everyone has participated, ending with the facilitator.

- Visual Moment (3 min):

Gently pull the network so that everyone feels the connection.

Key phrase: "This network represents that we are connected. If someone needs anything, here are people who can help."

If it is a recurring activity, the facilitator adds: "Each session adds new threads to this network, also joining those who have been before."

- Final photo (optional):

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Ask them to lower the net to the ground and, if they use body tape, to stick their paper to the corresponding thread.

When lifting the net, it will be tense and colorful: Ideal moment for group photo!

- Reflection (optional):

"What do you Feel when you see this network? How do you think these connections can help you in the future?"

Invite them to take their word as a reminder of what they have lived.

- Variant (for virtual groups):

Use a tool like Miro or Jamboard: Everyone writes their word in a digital post-it and draws lines connecting them. Share the final image by chat.

16.5 Why does this dynamic work?

- Emotional: The metaphor of the network reinforces belonging and mutual support.
- Visual: The photo remains as a tangible memory of the teamwork.
- Flexible: It can be adapted to face-to-face, virtual or hybrid sessions.

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Online Dynamics (Virtual activities)

1. Co-creation in Virtual Whiteboard

1.1 Objective

- Encourage creative collaboration.

1.2 Duration

- 5-10 minutes.

1.3 Materials

- Virtual Whiteboard (there are many options:
<https://tech.co/project-management-software/best-online-whiteboards>)

1.4 Development

- Share a Jamboard and ask each participant to add a single stroke to the collective drawing.
- Rule: They can not modify the stroke of others, only contribute theirs.
- Final reflection: "How did the drawing change with each contribution?"

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2. Talking Cameras

2.1 Objective

- Discover things in common visually.

2.2 Duration

- 5-10 minutes.

2.3 Materials

- Video call with camera available.

2.4 Development

- Everyone turns off the camera. The facilitator says, "Turn on the camera only if..." (e.g. "...they have a pet").
- Those who meet the condition turn on the camera and share briefly if they wish (e.g. "My dog is named Thor").
- The facilitator encourages you to participate by asking questions.

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3. I Draw with the Wrong Hand

3.1 Objective

- Laugh and enhance creativity under restrictions.

3.2 Duration

- 10-15 minutes.

3.3 Materials

- Paper and pen or markers.

3.4 Development

- Each person draws their self-portrait with their non-dominant hand (without lifting the pencil).
- They show them on camera to encourage the ability to laugh at oneself.
- One volunteer draws another participant (secretly) and others guess. Several rounds are made.

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4. Simon says 2.0

4.1 Objective

- Improve attention and coordination.

4.2 Duration

- 10-15 minutes.

4.3 Materials

- Video call with camera available.

4.4 Development

- The facilitator gives conflicting orders (e.g. "Simon says: Lift your left arm" while raising their right); participants have to do what they say, not what they do.
- Whoever does it wrong, is out until the next round.

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5. Two Lies and a Truth

5.1 Objective

- Generate confidence and curiosity.

5.2 Duration

- 5-10 minutes.

5.3 Materials

- Paper and pen.

5.4 Development

- Each participant writes 2 lies and 1 truth about themselves.
- In turn, one participant reads their 3 sentences and the others vote in the chat which one they think is true.
- Tip: Use curious data (e.g. "Once I saved a koala").

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6. Kiss Camera

6.1 Objective

- Generate complicity and quick laughter.

6.2 Duration

- 5-10 minutes.

6.3 Materials

- Video call with camera available.

6.4 Development

- Pin 2-3 participants with the camera and ask them:
 - Play “rock, paper, scissors” with exaggerated mimicry.
 - Imitate each other (e.g. postures, faces).
 - Represent a scene (e.g. "First day of school").

Why do all these dynamics work?

- They create a relaxed climate of confidence.
- They break the physical barrier of the screen and demonstrate that online sessions can also be dynamic.
- They include everyone: The participants are rotated so that no one is left out.

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